

1 **Learning effects in over-ground running gait retraining: A 6-month follow-up of**
2 **a quasi-randomized controlled trial**

3

4 *This is an Accepted Manuscript of an article published by Taylor & Francis in the Journal of Sports*

5 *Sciences on 27 April 2024, available at:*

6 <https://www.tandfonline.com/doi/full/10.1080/02640414.2024.2323849> .

7

8 **Original research article**

9

10 **Authors:**

11 Pieter Van den Berghe, Rud Derie, Joeri Gerlo, Senne Bonnaerens, Pieter Fiers, Ine Van Caekenberghe,
12 Dirk De Clercq, Veerle Segers

13 Biomechanics and Motor Control of Human Movement, Department of Movement and Sport Sciences,
14 Ghent University, Belgium

15

16 **Author Information' note:**

17 Shared co-first authorship.

18

19 **Corresponding Author:**

20 Email: pieter.vandenbergh@ugent.be

21 Under Affiliation: Department of Movement and Sports Sciences, Ghent University. Watersportlaan 2,
22 Ghent, 9000 Belgium

23 Under Current address: Department of Rehabilitation Sciences, Ghent University. Corneel
24 Heymanslaan 10, 9000 Belgium

Learning effects in over-ground running gait retraining: A six-month follow-up of a quasi-randomized controlled trial

Aim & methods

To evaluate if lower impact running persists half a year after completing a biofeedback-based retraining program.

Results

At follow-up, impacts were not decreased in the experimental group by retention only, but proved to be lower after recall.

Biofeedback

Intervention and testing

3-week running program: six monitored sessions of 20 minutes at approximately 10 km/h on an athletic track

2 groups of high-impact runners:

10 **controls** 🎵 and 10 **experimentals** 🎵🔊

Lab tests before and six months after the program

Implication

Impact reduction has been made possible in a training environment using wearable technology via biofeedback on an impact measure. **The biofeedback-based program did not induce clear motor learning, but a substantial impact reduction was recallable** through simple cueing (i.e., “run as at the end of the program”) without biofeedback.

26 **Abstract**

27 This study evaluated learning and recall effects following a feedback-based retraining program. A 6-
28 month follow-up of a quasi-randomized controlled trial was performed with and without recall. Twenty
29 runners were assigned to experimental or control groups and completed a 3-week running program.
30 A body-worn system collected axial tibial acceleration and provided real-time feedback on peak tibial
31 acceleration for six running sessions in an athletic training facility. The experimental group received
32 music-based biofeedback in a faded feedback scheme. The controls received tempo-synchronized
33 music as a placebo for blinding purposes. The peak tibial acceleration and vertical loading rate of the
34 ground reaction force were determined in a lab at baseline and six months following the intervention
35 to assess retention and recall. The impacts of the experimental group substantially decreased at follow-
36 up following a simple verbal recall (i.e., run as at the end of the program): peak tibial acceleration:-
37 32%, $p=0.018$; vertical loading rate:-34%, $p=0.006$. No statistically significant changes were found
38 regarding the retention of the impact variables. The impact magnitudes did not change over time in
39 the control group. The biofeedback-based intervention did not induce clear learning at follow-up,
40 however, a substantial impact reduction was recallable through simple cueing in the absence of
41 biofeedback.

42 **Key words:** motor learning, biofeedback, biomechanics, motor control, music

43 Introduction

44 The notion of gait retraining in human running has recently been studied in relation to the objective of
45 impact reduction (Cheung et al., 2018; Clansey et al., 2014; Futrell et al., 2021) and, relatedly, to injury
46 risk management (Chan et al., 2018; Morris et al., 2020). A clinical trial conducted by Chan and
47 colleagues (2018) focused on gait retraining for impact reduction. The trial included an evaluation of
48 running-related injuries up to one year after the retraining program. Novice runners were initially
49 screened on the vertical loading rate, which is an impact measure and represents the steepness of the
50 force-time waveform in the early stance phase of running gait. Those with a moderate-to-high vertical
51 loading rate were studied further. In a randomized controlled design, the experimental group received
52 a gait instruction (i.e., “run softer”) and real-time visual biofeedback on their vertical ground reaction
53 force. This feedback gave them information about a modifiable biomechanical metric and is provided
54 with the goal of being able to manipulate it at will. By the end of the program, the experimental group
55 had successfully lowered their vertical loading rate. One year later, this group showed a 62% decrease
56 in total running-related injury risk compared with the control group. Although the mechanisms for this
57 reduction in overuse injuries are unclear and multiple ex vivo studies refute the idea of higher loading
58 rates playing a key role in the pathophysiology of biological tissues (Edwards, 2018; Loundagin et al.,
59 2017; Zitnay et al., 2020), the results of this clinical trial suggest that retraining for lower-impact
60 running can have a positive effect on injury risk. While these findings are intriguing, Chan and
61 colleagues did not document the if the impacts were reduced at follow-up. So, it is unknown if the
62 motor system adapted in time. Without a persistent change in mechanics, implying long term retention
63 of the gait modifications, injury risk is not likely to be altered according to Bowser et al. (2018).
64 Therefore, it is warranted to explore gait retraining for impact reduction in distance running from a
65 motor learning perspective.

66 Wearable technology may help learn motor skills like lower impact running outside of a lab. We can
67 use body worn equipment to identify the axial peak tibial acceleration (PTA_a). PTA_a has been
68 successfully correlated with the maximum vertical loading rate at multiple speeds in level running (Van
69 den Berghe et al., 2019). Runners can reduce PTA_a with the simple use of real-time feedback on PTA_a
70 (Clansey et al., 2014; Van den Berghe, Derie, et al., 2022). In one study, PTA_a has been reduced by
71 about 30% following a 3-week retraining program in a laboratory setting (Clansey et al., 2014). More
72 recently, a feedback-based retraining program has been completed in a controlled training
73 environment (Van den Berghe, Derie, et al., 2022), which also resulted in a clear reduction in the PTA_a
74 upon its completion. However, there hasn't been much research on the learning effects of using real-
75 time biofeedback without gait instruction to reduce impacts (Clansey et al., 2014).

76 Gait-retraining studies often focus implicitly or explicitly on the immediate effects of impact reduction
77 and on variables potentially related to injury risk such as ground reaction forces (Chan et al., 2018;
78 Clansey et al., 2014; Crowell & Davis, 2011; Derie et al., 2022; Van den Berghe et al., 2021). This
79 approach is useful for examining the acute sensitivity of running-related variables to feedback
80 interventions, but neglects long term motor learning that may occur. Altering a motor pattern that has
81 been reinforced over millions of cycles might be possible if guidance and practice are provided (Bowser
82 et al., 2018; Davis & Futrell, 2016). Data from a recent report on gait retraining, including the use of
83 visual feedback on axial tibial acceleration and an instruction to run softer, suggests that impact
84 reduction can be achieved and maintained up to one year (Bowser et al., 2018); however, the
85 retraining program was performed in a lab environment and without control group. More recently,
86 feedback-based gait retraining targeting a reduction in PTA_a in a controlled training center has been
87 studied in a quasi-randomized controlled trial (Van den Berghe, Derie, et al., 2022). Furthermore, the
88 impact reduction achieved while receiving the real-time, music-based feedback on PTA_a was relatively
89 reproducible through simple verbal cueing without requiring this feedback (Derie et al., 2022; Van den
90 Berghe, Derie, et al., 2022). Although the studies performed by Van den Berghe and Derie et al. have
91 been performed in a controlled trial design (Derie et al., 2022; Van den Berghe, Derie, et al., 2022),
92 they are limited to the short-term influence of the biofeedback. Thus, an evaluation should be carried
93 forward to examine if the impact reduction persists over time and whether lower impact running is
94 recallable.

95 In this study, we took an extended approach to evaluating learning effects and asked whether lower
96 impact running persists and is recallable half a year after completing the biofeedback-based retraining
97 program. This question is well suited to the use of retention testing, which is our primary method for
98 assessing the long-term retention of motor skill learning. Researchers conducting motor learning
99 studies often include retention testing as a means to determine the durability and persistence of the
100 learned skills over time (Bowser et al., 2018; Bramah et al., 2019; Clansey et al., 2014; Futrell et al.,
101 2020). Using retention testing provides information about the persistence of the motor adaptation,
102 and helps advance our understanding of the learning process and potential interventions for skill
103 retention. The retention testing phase typically occurs after an initial training or learning phase, where
104 participants undergo practice to acquire or improve a specific motor skill or task. During retention
105 testing, participants may perform the previously learned motor skill without any additional training or
106 biofeedback (Davis & Futrell, 2016). The performance is then compared to their past performance level
107 (Bowser et al., 2018; Clansey et al., 2014). Here, the main objective of retention testing is to determine
108 whether the motor adaptation is retained over time or if it diminishes. Furthermore, we evaluated
109 whether the impact reduction is recallable through a simple reminder. Based on the few studies on

110 this topic that included some form of retention testing (Bowser et al., 2018; Clansley et al., 2014), we
111 hypothesized that motor learning occurs and the impact reduction would persist without and with
112 recall.

113 **Methods**

114 *Experimental design.* This follow-up of a parallel, quasi-randomized controlled trial is part of a study
115 series (Derie et al., 2022; Van den Berghe, Derie, et al., 2022). Hence, the study cohort is identical to
116 preceding studies in which the immediate effects on impact reduction and running biomechanics have
117 been documented (Derie et al., 2022; Van den Berghe, Derie, et al., 2022). Reporting of the study
118 followed the CONSORT statement (Figure 1). The institutional ethics committee reviewed and
119 approved the experimental procedure. We carried out the methods following their guidelines and
120 regulations. Interested volunteers completed an online questionnaire and made an appointment with
121 the research team.

122 Participants enrolled in the first (screening) phase were invited to participate in the second
123 (intervention and follow-up) part of the study if they fulfilled the following inclusion criteria: aged 18–
124 60 years, no contraindication to performing running activity, typically running 15 km per week or more
125 spread over at least two weekly sessions. To fully qualify, participants were required to attend a brief
126 running impact screening in a sports laboratory in which only tibial acceleration was collected while
127 running at ~ 3.2 m/s. Extended methods have been made available and further describe the data
128 collection of the screening phase performed (Van den Berghe, Derie, et al., 2022). We iteratively
129 invited the subject with the highest PTA_a for further participation in the study and the first twenty who
130 agreed to participate were enrolled in the intervention phase (Derie et al., 2022; Van den Berghe,
131 Derie, et al., 2022). These participants were assigned to either the retraining group ($n = 10$, age:
132 32.1 ± 7.8 years, body mass: 71.5 ± 18.3 kg, body height: 1.74 ± 0.11 m, weekly running volume: 27 ± 10
133 km, self-reported training speed: 2.9 ± 0.3 m/s, males/females: 5/5) or the control group ($n = 10$, age:
134 39.1 ± 10.4 years, body mass: 69.9 ± 12.8 kg, body height: 1.74 ± 0.11 m, weekly running volume: 37 ± 18
135 km, self-reported training speed: 2.9 ± 0.4 m/s) and were blinded to the group assignment. The sample
136 size was chosen so that short-term effects in impact reduction could be observed in a quasi-
137 randomized controlled design through the application of music-based biofeedback (Derie et al., 2022;
138 Van den Berghe, Derie, et al., 2022).

139 Two lab visits were scheduled, prior to and after the intervention, during the 6th month of the follow-
140 up. Both tests were performed while running continuously on an indoor track (Figure 2) at a pace of
141 2.9 ± 0.2 m·s⁻¹ in mimicked pairs of the participants' habitual running footwear. An overview of the
142 subjects' habitual footwear and matching laboratory footwear has been made available (Derie et al.,

143 2022). The first visit comprised a 5-min warm-up that served as a familiarization to the setup, and a
144 continuous run of about 25 minutes to determine baseline values. The second visit also comprised a
145 warm-up which was followed by two running conditions to assess learning: the retention condition
146 and the recall condition. In case of retention testing, participants may intentionally produce the
147 desired gait pattern during assessments, making it difficult to discern if motor learning and retention
148 have truly occurred (Futrell et al., 2020). Therefore, to avoid response bias, participants were
149 intentionally distracted in the retention condition. They performed a cognitive distraction task each
150 time when passing the lab's measurement zone. Specifically, a modified Stroop test started each time
151 a participant would enter the measurement zone (Figure 2, video S1). We projected a written name of
152 a color, in which the name of the color and the color of the text not necessarily matched (video S1).
153 They were instructed to say the color of the text out loud, but not the word itself. Participants were
154 asked to say the word accurately and as fast as possible. For the recall condition, the participants were
155 asked to reproduce the running technique from the intervention six months earlier. We used a simple
156 verbal instruction for all subjects: *"Try running as you did in the final session of the retraining program.*
157 *"* The instructed running speed was in agreement with that of the running program (Derie et al., 2022).

158 *Running program.* Both groups were subjected to a 3-week running program in a supervised training
159 facility (Van den Berghe, Derie, et al., 2022). The 3-week schedule and the six sessions were similar to
160 the program design made by Clansey et al. (2014). Each running session consisted of twenty minutes
161 of running with music. Participants were told to run with specifically selected music tailored to them.
162 The music-only group listened to music tracks that were suited for synchronization to the individual's
163 running cadence. As such, the smart music player adjust and could mirror the beats per minute of the
164 music to the steps per minute of the runner. The experimental group additionally received real-time
165 feedback on PTA_a. This feedback was music-based wherein the music was distorted at medium and
166 high PTA_a (Van den Berghe, Derie, et al., 2022; Van den Berghe et al., 2021). This impact measure was
167 converted into noise that is perceptible by the runner, wherein the conversion is done based on a
168 predefined relationship between perceived distortion levels and imposed distortion levels (Lorenzoni
169 et al., 2019). Specifically, pink noise was superimposed on the music if the peak tibial acceleration was
170 $\geq 70\%$ of the runner's starting PTA_a (Van den Berghe, Derie, et al., 2022). This starting value was
171 determined during the 5-minute warming-up run without any musical feedback (Van den Berghe,
172 Derie, et al., 2022). The limb exhibiting the highest mean PTA_a in this period was considered dominant
173 and used further. It has been concluded that a faded feedback approach is superior to continuous
174 feedback for retaining motor skills (Winstein, 1991). Fading of the feedback encourages internalization
175 of the altered running form, (Davis & Futrell, 2016) implying the motor skill learning may benefit from
176 fading the feedback on PTA_a in time. Therefore, we implemented a two-phased feedback scheme

177 desired to stimulate motor learning (Van den Berghe, Derie, et al., 2022). The fading of the biofeedback
178 prevents the reliance on the feedback and enhances the internalization, and thus learning, of the new
179 motor pattern.(Davis & Futrell, 2016) In the first (acquisition) phase, feedback was continuously
180 provided which helps to develop the connection between the extrinsic feedback and the internal
181 sensory cues associated with the desired target behaviour.(Davis & Futrell, 2016) So, the first two
182 sessions of running comprised of 20 min of continuous biofeedback. In the second (transfer) phase,
183 the feedback was systematically removed, meaning the time of biofeedback provision gradually
184 decreased in the last four sessions. We did not inform the experimental group about this faded
185 feedback scheme in which the volume of the feedback varied. The running speed was steered to
186 approximately $2.9 \text{ m}\cdot\text{s}^{-1}$ throughout these sessions (Van den Berghe, Derie, et al., 2022), which
187 corresponded to the mean self-reported endurance training speed of the participants. Please see
188 reference (Van den Berghe, Derie, et al., 2022) for a detailed description of the retraining protocol. In
189 this 3-week program, participants were free to choose whether to maintain the gait modifications
190 during their regular training routine. Following completion of the program, participants were advised
191 to adopt their new gait pattern in their regular running practice (Chan et al., 2018).

192 *Materials and lab-based measurements.* Participants were equipped with a wearable sensor system to
193 determine PTA_a in the lab visits. The main components of this system were two accelerometers
194 (LIS331, Sparkfun, Colorado, USA, sampling rate: 1000Hz/axis) wired to a microcontroller. This
195 microcontroller was connected to a 7-inch tablet strapped to a stripped backpack (Van den Berghe et
196 al., 2019, 2020). Sensor weight and the method of attachment plays an important role in data quality
197 according to a systematic review (Norris et al., 2014). The accelerometers were lightweight with a mass
198 of less than 3 grams per unit. Our method of attachment was similar to an approach that has been
199 shown to be reliable within and between sessions of over-ground, level running (Van den Berghe et
200 al., 2019). Each sensor was firmly taped to the skin at eight centimeters above the malleolus medialis
201 on the anteromedial aspect of a lower limb. Prior to this action, the skin in the vicinity of the selected
202 sensor location got pre-stretched with sports tape to ensure a rigid coupling. Then, a test leader
203 visually aligned the vertical axis of each accelerometer with the longitudinal axis of the tibia. Thus, we
204 assumed the acceleration collected corresponds to the acceleration of the tibial bone. The body-worn
205 sensors permitted participants to run continuously along a 30-m instrumented running track (Derie et
206 al., 2022). Two pairs of photo gates were positioned in the measurement zone 6 meter apart. Two
207 force platforms (AMTI, Watertown MA, USA; dimensions: 2.1·0.5-m and 1.2·1.2-m; sampling rate:
208 2000Hz) were situated in the center of the measurement zone. These platforms had covers on top
209 which were flush with the running track. Acceleration and force plate data were synchronized in time

210 up to millimeter accuracy by applying a synchronization protocol described elsewhere (Van den Berghe
211 et al., 2019).

212 *Statistical analysis.* Baseline demographic data were analyzed with independent t-tests to determine
213 presence of differences between the experimental and control groups. Running variables of interest
214 were PTA_a and the vertical loading rate. The PTA_a was defined as the maximal positive axial acceleration
215 of the lower leg while the foot contacted the ground. The events of foot-ground contact were derived
216 from the vertical ground reaction force. This force was filtered using a 2nd order, zero-lag low-pass
217 Butterworth filter with a 60Hz cut-off frequency. The force threshold was set at 20 N. The vertical
218 loading rate was calculated as the maximum value of the first derivative of the ground reaction force
219 in the first 0.050s of stance. These variables were analyzed via linear mixed model with an $\alpha = 0.05$
220 (JASP 0.16.3). The fixed effect variables we entered were Group (experimental, control) and Conditions
221 (baseline, retention, recall) and the subjects as random effects grouping factor. In the case of a
222 significant group \times time interaction, post-hoc comparisons were conducted with a Bonferroni
223 correction. Cohen's d was calculated to determine the magnitude of the effect ($d < 0.2$ – very small,
224 $0.2 \leq d < 0.5$ – small, $0.5 \leq d < 0.8$ – medium, $d \geq 0.8$ – large). Handling missing data is an important,
225 yet difficult and complex task when analyzing results of randomized trials. Therefore, in a post-hoc
226 analysis, missing values were replaced using single imputation of the mean (Jakobsen et al., 2017). In
227 simple mean imputation, missing values are replaced by the mean for the variable of interest.

228 **Results**

229 Two experimental subjects were lost because of an injury or due to a personal reason after the
230 retraining phase was completed. The follow-up happened after 183 ± 9 days (mean \pm standard
231 deviation). There were no significant differences between groups in the running variables of interest
232 at baseline. There were significant group \times time interactions for PTA_a ($F=3.369$, $p=0.047$) and vertical
233 loading rate ($F=4.345$, $p=0.021$). Subsequent pairwise comparisons revealed only a significant change
234 from Baseline-Recall for the experimental group: PTA_a (Mean difference=-2.43 g or -31%, $t=3.905$,
235 $p=0.007$, $d=1.295$) and vertical loading rate (Mean difference=-30.5 BW/s or -34%, $t=4.231$, $p=0.003$,
236 $d=1.195$) (Figure 3, Table S1). For the control group, no significant changes occurred at 6-month follow-
237 up in either the Retention or Recall compared with Baseline levels. The post-hoc analysis with imputed
238 missing data revealed that the change between Baseline and Retention in the experimental group
239 became statistically significant for PTA_a ($|\text{Mean difference}| = -1.96$ g, $t = 3.429$, $p = 0.023$, $d = 1.065$)
240 (Table S1).

241 **Discussion**

242 The current study evaluated retention and recall effects of a biofeedback-driven program of gait
243 retraining that stimulated impact reduction in running. The hypothesis was that motor learning would
244 occur, which was only partially supported. First, we addressed learning from the perspective of
245 retention. We found no significant change in impact magnitudes after six months. Contrary to our
246 expectation, the reductions in PTA_a and vertical loading rate following completion of the retraining
247 program did not persist in this small cohort. Our original research data challenge the idea that just
248 three weeks of gait retraining can permanently change people's running form, and countermand a
249 recent systematic review concluding that real-time tibial acceleration feedback can reduce PTA_a for
250 periods to 12 months when the feedback has been removed (Li et al., 2023). We will discuss several
251 potential reasons for this discrepancy later. Second, from the perspective of recall and immediately
252 after the retention condition we asked the experimental group asked to reproduce the running form
253 from the last retraining session. They did achieve a significant reduction in impact, which suggests that
254 the changes needed for impact reduction are recallable long time after completing a 3-week
255 intervention. The reduction in impact at six months (mean difference in PTA_a: -2.43 g; vertical loading
256 rate: -30.5 B/W) aligns well with the impact reduction observed post intervention (mean difference in
257 PTA: -2.55 g; vertical loading rate: -31.5 B/W) in the same testing environment (Derie et al., 2022).
258 Although the new motor pattern was not fully ingrained yet, it is encouraging that participants were
259 able to recall it with just a simple reminder. This suggests that verbal reminders given by a practitioner
260 can help runners remember the self-discovered gait modifications a long time after finishing the
261 program. The changes in impact that we observed in the Follow up condition were likely because
262 people consciously tried to modify their running form, not because a new skill became persistent.
263 Looking at the group who did not receive the biofeedback, the impact magnitudes remained stable
264 after half a year. This finding supports a previous observation that impact magnitudes of a group of
265 runners during running on level ground are reliable when tested again later (Van den Berghe et al.,
266 2019).

267 Our results contradict the results reported by Bowser et al. (2018) who suggested that impact
268 reduction can be achieved and maintained up to one year following running gait retraining. A few
269 possible explanations for this discrepancy are given. A possible explanation lies in the difference in
270 training and testing environments. Previous studies conducted the intervention and retention testing
271 in the same environment, resulting in participants spending a considerable amount of time in an
272 artificial lab setting during the retraining. As a result, when these participants reappeared in the same
273 lab for the retention testing, there is a higher chance of instinctive recall and response bias. In our
274 study, the retraining program and learning evaluation were conducted at different locations, meaning
275 the participants performed the learning tests in an environment different from their practice sessions.

276 Furthermore, a cognitive distraction task (i.e., modified Stroop test) was added to our retention testing
277 to limit the possibility of performance bias during the data collection (Futrell et al., 2020). It is unlikely
278 that this task has influenced the impact magnitudes because previous research has detected impact
279 reduction during distracted running immediately post-retraining (Cheung et al., 2018). Another
280 possible explanation is that participants did not have enough practice time to achieve clear motor
281 learning. The statistically non-significant reduction in impact magnitudes at Retention suggests that
282 participants may need more sessions than anticipated. Our study design was largely based on that of
283 Clansy and colleagues (2014) wherein participants receive only six practice sessions, while studies
284 reporting impact reduction at follow-up involved eight practice sessions (Bowser et al., 2018; Crowell
285 & Davis, 2011). Based on our observations, we recommend tailoring the number of sessions in the
286 retraining program to each individual's needs. It is plausible that participants entered the transfer
287 phase too soon and could have benefited further from more continuous feedback as provided in the
288 acquisition phase. So, we suggest to start fading the feedback only if the participant has shown
289 significant improvement for a while. This reduction can be qualitatively analyzed by a supervisor closely
290 monitoring the participant or quantitatively analyzed through a change-point analysis (Van den Berghe
291 et al., 2020). Additionally, occasional refresher training or recall sessions may be beneficial for
292 achieving motor learning eventually.

293 These results have relevance to the users, coaching staff and sports scientists currently interested in
294 the effects of wearable devices that stimulate less PTA_a in running at a comfortable running speed.
295 Real-time biofeedback has been found to be the most effective way of reducing impact, and runners
296 tend to employ a distal strategy unless given specific cues (Napier et al., 2015). The distal strategy for
297 reducing PTA_a has been found in this sample of habitual rearfoot striking runners who used the music-
298 based biofeedback device (Derie et al., 2022), with plantar pressure analysis showing it spans the entire
299 foot strike spectrum. More specifically, eight out of ten kept landing on their heel region, one switched
300 to midfoot striking and another one to forefoot striking following the running retraining intervention
301 (Derie et al., 2022). The vast majority kept rearfoot striking and increased the foot strike angle by +5°
302 (i.e., more dorsiflexion at touchdown) on average. This finding is in agreement with our previous cross-
303 sectional studies (Van den Berghe, Breine, et al., 2022; Van den Berghe, Warlop, et al., 2022). Namely,
304 at a comfortable steady-state running speed on level ground, heel-toe runners who experience
305 relatively low PTA_a during level running are more likely to perform an obvious rearfoot strike. Although
306 the major movement changes due to the biofeedback have been studied, participant characteristics
307 potentially influencing how easily humans motorically adapt (e.g., motor coordination, training history)
308 were not included here. Crowell and colleagues (2011) disclosed that all participants in their running
309 retraining program reported that the new way of running felt natural after six practice sessions.

310 Although participants had more practice time during the retraining sessions of the current study, it is
311 plausible that the changes in running style for reducing impact did not feel natural after our six-session
312 program. Furthermore, it has been shown that endurance training volume can affect running
313 biomechanics (Boyer et al., 2014; Verheul et al., 2017), and we acknowledge that the cohort examined
314 in the present study demonstrated variation in weekly training volume and presumably also in
315 experience of endurance training prior to enrollment. The running mileage following completion of the
316 retraining intervention was also not tracked, which is another variable that may influence the
317 retention. In future research, it would be valuable to ask participants how they perceive the modified
318 gait pattern (e.g., level of difficulty, confidence, etc.) and to track their training profile because it may
319 help explaining why people chose not to use it on a typical run but can recall it.

320 A clear relationship between PTA_a and injury risk in running is yet to be established (Sheerin et al.,
321 2019). The use of these kind of biofeedback devices as a potential tool for injury risk management
322 stands or falls with their effect on the running-related injury risk eventually. For this reason, efficacy
323 trials are needed to determine whether an intervention (e.g., impact reduction) produces the expected
324 result (e.g., an altered injury risk) under ideal circumstances. Randomized controlled clinical trials
325 would be helpful to determine if reducing PTA_a alters the injury risk in very large groups of runners or
326 not, and if the large-scale intervention would result in a persistent change in running mechanics. Some
327 might wonder whether reducing impacts with large effect sizes leads to changes in general indicators
328 of musculoskeletal loading. To address this, our research unit has conducted comprehensive gait
329 analysis on the experimental group of heel-toe runners that was beyond the scope of the present
330 study. In this group of small sample size, we observed no statistically significant change in the
331 maximum vertical ground reaction force, the peak moment and power of the ankle and knee joints, or
332 the muscular work done at these joints (Derie et al., 2022). Based on the data at hand, practitioners
333 should not assume that a change in the commonly used impact metric PTA_a corresponds with a similar
334 change in the aforementioned indicators of musculoskeletal loading. Wearable sensor systems that
335 interact with runners to reduce PTA_a may still be useful in incorporating variation into a training regime
336 of distance runners.

337 The current study is limited by its small sample size with missing data. Simulating experiments in small
338 samples has shown that results can be inconsistent compared to the original large samples, leading to
339 both false positive and false negative outcomes (Oakes, 2017). The issue of incomplete data is common
340 in longitudinal study designs. If we applied mean imputation, the interpretation of the results would
341 be different. In such case, we could have detected a retention effect for the feedback variable.
342 However, using single imputation often underestimates variability because unobserved values are
343 given equal weight to observed values in the analysis (Jakobsen et al., 2017). The decrease in variability

344 was noticeable in the small experimental group, indicating the need to increase the sample size in
345 future research post-COVID pandemic. Another limitation is that the intervention took place in a
346 training environment (Van den Berghe, Derie, et al., 2022), but the follow-up testing was conducted in
347 a laboratory setting. Unsupervised follow-up testing in the field with wearables monitoring larger
348 samples is warranted to validate the results of these gait-retraining interventions.

349 **Conclusion**

350 The biofeedback intervention did not induce a clear learning effect after six months. Interestingly, a
351 substantial impact reduction was recallable at the six-month follow up through simple verbal cueing.
352 Participants could recall and reenact the impact reduction in the absence of feedback on PTA_a. In the
353 absence of additional feedback sessions between the end of the intervention and follow-up, a verbal
354 recall by a supervisor or coach appears effective to evoke the impact reduction achieved during the
355 intervention.

356 **References**

- 357 Bowser, B. J., Fellin, R., Milner, C. E., Pohl, M. B., & Davis, I. S. (2018). Reducing impact loading in
358 runners: A one-year follow-up. *Medicine and Science in Sports and Exercise*, *50*(12), 2500–2506.
359 <https://doi.org/10.1249/MSS.0000000000001710>
- 360 Boyer, K. A., Silvernail, J. F., & Hamill, J. (2014). The Role of Running Mileage on Coordination
361 Patterns in Running. *Journal of Applied Biomechanics*, *30*(5), 649–654.
362 <https://doi.org/10.1123/jab.2013-0261>
- 363 Bramah, C., Preece, S. J., Gill, N., & Herrington, L. (2019). A 10% Increase in Step Rate Improves
364 Running Kinematics and Clinical Outcomes in Runners With Patellofemoral Pain at 4 Weeks and
365 3 Months. *American Journal of Sports Medicine*, *47*(14), 3406–3413.
366 <https://doi.org/10.1177/0363546519879693>
- 367 Chan, Z. Y., Zhang, J. H., Au, I. P., An, W. W., Shum, G. L., Ng, G. Y., & Cheung, R. T. (2018). Gait
368 Retraining for the Reduction of Injury Occurrence in Novice Distance Runners: 1-Year Follow-up
369 of a Randomized Controlled Trial. *The American Journal of Sports Medicine*, *46*(2), 388–395.
370 <https://doi.org/10.1177/0363546517736277>
- 371 Cheung, R. T. H., An, W. W., Au, I. P. H., Zhang, J. H., Chan, Z. Y. S., & MacPhail, A. J. (2018). Control of
372 impact loading during distracted running before and after gait retraining in runners. *Journal of*
373 *Sports Sciences*, *36*(13), 1497–1501. <https://doi.org/10.1080/02640414.2017.1398886>
- 374 Clansy, A. C., Hanlon, M., Wallace, E. S., Nevill, A., & Lake, M. J. (2014). Influence of Tibial shock
375 feedback training on impact loading and running economy. *Medicine and Science in Sports and*
376 *Exercise*, *46*(5), 973–981. <https://doi.org/10.1249/MSS.0000000000000182>
- 377 Crowell, H. P., & Davis, I. S. (2011). Gait retraining to reduce lower extremity loading in runners.
378 *Clinical Biomechanics*, *26*(1), 78–83. <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.clinbiomech.2010.09.003>

- 379 Davis, I. S., & Futrell, E. (2016). Gait Retraining: Altering the Fingerprint of Gait. *Physical Medicine and*
380 *Rehabilitation Clinics of North America*, 27(1), 339–355.
381 <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.pmr.2015.09.002>
- 382 Derie, R., Van den Berghe, P., Gerlo, J., Bonnaerens, S., Caekenberghe, I. Van, Fiers, P., De Clercq, D.,
383 & Segers, V. (2022). Biomechanical adaptations following a music-based biofeedback gait
384 retraining program to reduce peak tibial accelerations. *Scandinavian Journal of Medicine &*
385 *Science in Sports*, 32(7), 1142–1152. <https://doi.org/10.1111/sms.14162>
- 386 Edwards, W. B. (2018). Modeling Overuse Injuries in Sport as a Mechanical Fatigue Phenomenon.
387 *Exercise and Sport Sciences Reviews*, 46(4), 224–231.
388 <https://doi.org/10.1249/JES.000000000000163>
- 389 Futrell, E. E., Gross, K. D., Mullineaux, D. R., & Davis, I. S. (2021). Exerted running results in altered
390 impact mechanics and footstrike patterns following gait retraining. *Journal of Sports Sciences*,
391 39(11), 1302–1311. <https://doi.org/10.1080/02640414.2020.1868089>
- 392 Futrell, E. E., Gross, K. D., Reisman, D., Mullineaux, D. R., & Davis, I. S. (2020). Transition to forefoot
393 strike reduces load rates more effectively than altered cadence. *Journal of Sport and Health*
394 *Science*, 9(3), 248–257. <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.jshs.2019.07.006>
- 395 Jakobsen, J. C., Gluud, C., Wetterslev, J., & Winkel, P. (2017). When and how should multiple
396 imputation be used for handling missing data in randomised clinical trials – a practical guide
397 with flowcharts. *BMC Medical Research Methodology*, 17(1), 162.
398 <https://doi.org/10.1186/s12874-017-0442-1>
- 399 Li, X., Yu, J., Bai, J., Huang, H., Ying, S., Wang, A., & Wang, P. (2023). The Effect of Real-Time Tibial
400 Acceleration Feedback on Running Biomechanics During Gait Retraining: A Systematic Review
401 and Meta-Analysis. *Journal of Sport Rehabilitation*, 1–13. <https://doi.org/10.1123/jsr.2022-0279>
- 402 Lorenzoni, V., Van den Berghe, P., Maes, P.-J., De Bie, T., De Clercq, D., & Leman, M. (2019). Design
403 and validation of an auditory biofeedback system for modification of running parameters.
404 *Journal on Multimodal User Interfaces*, 13(3), 167–180. [https://doi.org/10.1007/s12193-018-](https://doi.org/10.1007/s12193-018-0283-1)
405 [0283-1](https://doi.org/10.1007/s12193-018-0283-1)
- 406 Loundagin, L. L., Schmidt, T., & Edwards, W. B. (2017). Is the Mechanical Fatigue of Bone Influenced
407 More by the Impact or Active Phase of Running? *Journal of Biomechanical Engineering*, c, 1–32.
408 <https://doi.org/10.1115/1.4038288>
- 409 Morris, J. B., Goss, D. L., Miller, E. M., & Davis, I. S. (2020). Using real-time biofeedback to alter
410 running biomechanics: A randomized controlled trial. *Translational Sports Medicine*, 3(1), 63–
411 71. <https://doi.org/10.1002/tsm2.110>
- 412 Napier, C., Cochrane, C. K., Taunton, J. E., & Hunt, M. A. (2015). Gait modifications to change lower
413 extremity gait biomechanics in runners: a systematic review. *British Journal of Sports Medicine*,
414 49(21), 1382–1388. <https://doi.org/10.1136/bjsports-2014-094393>
- 415 Norris, M., Anderson, R., & Kenny, I. C. (2014). Method analysis of accelerometers and gyroscopes in
416 running gait: A systematic review. *Proceedings of the Institution of Mechanical Engineers, Part*
417 *P: Journal of Sports Engineering and Technology*, 228(1), 3–15.
418 <https://doi.org/10.1177/1754337113502472>

- 419 Oakes, L. M. (2017). Sample Size, Statistical Power, and False Conclusions in Infant Looking-Time
420 Research. *Infancy*, 22(4), 436–469. <https://doi.org/10.1111/infa.12186>
- 421 Sheerin, K. R., Reid, D., & Besier, T. F. (2019). The measurement of tibial acceleration in runners: A
422 review of the factors that can affect tibial acceleration during running and evidence-based
423 guidelines for its use. *Gait & Posture*, 67(September 2018), 12–24.
424 <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.gaitpost.2018.09.017>
- 425 Van den Berghe, P., Breine, B., Haeck, E., & De Clercq, D. (2022). One hundred marathons in 100
426 days: Unique biomechanical signature and the evolution of force characteristics and bone
427 density. *Journal of Sport and Health Science*, 11(3), 347–357.
428 <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.jshs.2021.03.009>
- 429 Van den Berghe, P., Derie, R., Bauwens, P., Gerlo, J., Segers, V., Leman, M., & De Clercq, D. (2022).
430 Reducing the peak tibial acceleration of running by music-based biofeedback: A quasi-
431 randomized controlled trial. *Scandinavian Journal of Medicine & Science in Sports*, 32(4), 698–
432 709. <https://doi.org/10.1111/sms.14123>
- 433 Van den Berghe, P., Gosseries, M., Gerlo, J., Lenoir, M., Leman, M., & De Clercq, D. (2020). Change-
434 Point Detection of Peak Tibial Acceleration in Overground Running Retraining. *Sensors*, 20(6),
435 1720. <https://doi.org/10.3390/s20061720>
- 436 Van den Berghe, P., Lorenzoni, V., Derie, R., Six, J., Gerlo, J., Leman, M., & De Clercq, D. (2021).
437 Music-based biofeedback to reduce tibial shock in over-ground running: a proof-of-concept
438 study. *Scientific Reports*, 11(1), 4091. <https://doi.org/10.1038/s41598-021-83538-w>
- 439 Van den Berghe, P., Six, J., Gerlo, J., Leman, M., & De Clercq, D. (2019). Validity and reliability of peak
440 tibial accelerations as real-time measure of impact loading during over-ground rearfoot running
441 at different speeds. *Journal of Biomechanics*, 86, 238–242.
442 <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.jbiomech.2019.01.039>
- 443 Van den Berghe, P., Warlop, L., Derie, R., Leman, M., De Clercq, D., & Breine, B. (2022). Foot strike
444 determines the center of pressure behavior and affects impact severity in heel-toe running.
445 *Journal of Sports Sciences*, 40(7), 808–820. <https://doi.org/10.1080/02640414.2021.2019991>
- 446 Verheul, J., Clansey, A. C., & Lake, M. J. (2017). Adjustments with running speed reveal
447 neuromuscular adaptations during landing associated with high mileage running training. *J Appl*
448 *Physiol*, 122, 653–665. <https://doi.org/10.1152/jappphysiol>
- 449 Winstein, C. J. (1991). Knowledge of results and motor learning - Implications for physical therapy. In
450 *Physical Therapy*. <https://doi.org/10.1093/ptj/71.2.140>
- 451 Zitnay, J. L., Seob Jung, G., Lin, A. H., Qin, Z., Li, Y., Michael Yu, S., Buehler, M. J., & Weiss, J. A. (2020).
452 *Accumulation of collagen molecular unfolding is the mechanism of cyclic fatigue damage and*
453 *failure in collagenous tissues*. <https://www.science.org>

454

455 **Funding**

456 This study was funded by Interreg EU (Nano4Sports-0217) and the Research Foundation–Flanders
457 (FWO.3F0.2015.0048.01). Mizuno Corporation provided product support. The manuscript was

458 published with support of the University Foundation from Belgium ('Uitgegeven met steun van de
459 Universitaire Stichting van België', WA-0473 to P.V.d.B).

460

461 **Confirmation of Ethical compliance**

462 All applicable international, national, and/or institutional guidelines to study humans were followed.
463 The study was approved by the UZ Gent ethics committee.

464

465 **Declaration of Interest**

466 The authors declare that the research was conducted in the absence of any financial relationships that
467 could be construed as a potential conflict of interest. One of the authors declared that he was an
468 editorial member of the journal at the time of submission. This had no impact on the peer review
469 process and the final decision.

470

471 **Acknowledgements**

472 Mizuno Corporation provided product support. We would like to acknowledge Prof. dr. Marc Leman
473 and IPEM for the assistance with the feedback device, and ing. Davy Spiessens for his assistance.

474

475 **Author's contribution Statement**

476 Pieter Van den Berghe: Methodology, Formal analysis, Visualization, Writing
477 Rud Derie: Investigation, Data Curation, Formal analysis, Writing - Original Draft
478 Joeri Gerlo: Software, Writing - Review & Editing
479 Senne Bonnaerens: Investigation, Writing - Review & Editing
480 Pieter Fiers: Investigation, Writing - Review & Editing
481 Ine Van Caekenberghe: Investigation, Writing - Review & Editing
482 Dirk De Clercq: Conceptualization, Funding acquisition, Writing - Review & Editing
483 Veerle Segers: Supervision, Resources, Project administration, Writing - Review & Editing

484

485 **Patient involvement statement**

486 Study participants were not involved in the design, conduct, interpretation, or translation of the
487 current research.

488

489 Data sharing statement

490 Data are available upon reasonable request.

491

492 Figures

493

494 Figure 1. CONSORT 2010 diagram: flow chart of study participants and conditions.

495
 496 Figure 2. Experimental setup. The running course is illustrated on top. The picture shows a participant
 497 during the Retest condition at follow-up. A Stroop test was presented to participants in front of the
 498 runway while they ran laps on an indoor track. The projection screen was positioned approximately 15
 499 m away from the center of the measurement zone. The associated video clip is supplemented (Video
 500 S1).

501

502 Figure 3. Peak axial tibial acceleration and vertical loading rate for the experimental and control groups at each of the time points. The Retention and Recall
 503 measurements were conducted within the same lab visit six months after the Baseline measurement. Error bars represent 95% confidence interval. * indicates
 504 a statistical difference from the post-hoc comparisons.

505 **Supplementary materials**

506 Table S1. Impact variables for the experimental and control groups. Descriptives are presented as
 507 mean (\pm SD).

Variable	Group	Baseline	Retention	Recall	Baseline-Retention	Baseline-Recall
PTAa (g)	Experimental (n = 8)	7.93 (\pm 1.87)	6.15 (\pm 0.95)	5.50 (\pm 1.13)	MD = -1.78 P = 0.110 d = 0.949 t = 2.862	MD = -2.43 P = 0.007* d = 1.295 t = 3.905
	imputed (n = 10)		6.15 (\pm 0.84)	5.50 (\pm 1.00)	MD = -1.96 P = 0.023* d = 1.065 t = 3.429	MD = -2.61 P < 0.001* d = 1.418 t = 4.565
	Control (n = 10)	7.23 (\pm 2.16)	6.91 (\pm 2.07)	6.79 (\pm 2.34)	MD = - 0.31 P = 1.000 d = 0.167 t = 0.561	MD = - 0.44 P = 1.000 d = 0.232 t = 0.782
VLRI (BW/s)	Experimental (n = 8)	96.3 (\pm 28.0)	84.4 (\pm 22.5)	65.8 (\pm 18.7)	MD = -11.8 P = 1.000 d = 0.462 t = 1.636	MD = -30.5 P = 0.003* d = 1.195 t = 4.231
	imputed (n = 10)		84.5 (\pm 19.8)	65.8 (\pm 16.4)	MD = -15.1 P = 0.349 d = 0.618 t = 2.370	MD = -33.9 P < 0.001* d = 1.383 t = 5.302
	Control (n = 10)	81.7 (\pm 22.0)	85.0 (\pm 30.2)	78.2 (\pm 28.6)	MD = 3.3 P = 1.000 d = -0.128 t = -0.505	MD = -3.5 P = 1.000 d = 0.137 t = 0.542

508 PTAa: Axial Peak Tibial Acceleration. VLRI: Instantaneous Vertical Loading Rate. MD: Mean Difference.
 509 d denotes Cohen’s d. P-value (Bonferroni) adjusted for comparing a family. T-value indicates the size
 510 of the difference relative to the variation in the sampled data. Imputed indicates single imputation
 511 of the mean for the variable of interest. * Significant independent t-test comparisons. Significance set
 512 at P < 0.05.

513 Video S1. A video clip of data collection during the Retention test. A modified Stroop test is projected
 514 on the screen in front of the measurement zone. A colored word appears when a participant entered
 515 the measurement zone and disappeared when leaving this zone, which was part of a straight section
 516 of the running lap. In the first video clip, the word blue (‘blauw’ in Dutch) is shown in black text. The
 517 participant is shouting ‘zwart’ which means black in Dutch. In the second clip, the word green (‘groen’
 518 in Dutch) is colored in green and is shouted accordingly.